

ReCcreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

José Hernández Vargas & Erik Stenberg
**Building, component, and
connector typologies of precast
concrete building systems**

Publisher / project	Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy
Project acronym	ReCreate
Deliverable	D1.2 Diagrams of building, component, and connector typologies
Lead beneficiary	KTH Royal Institute of Technology
Author(s)	José Hernández Vargas (KTH) & Erik Stenberg (KTH)
Dissemination level	Public
Cite this document	Hernández Vargas, J. & Stenberg, E. (2024). <i>Building, component, and connector typologies of precast concrete building systems</i> . The ReCreate Project.
Disclaimer	The content presented herein reflects the authors' views. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.

Abstract

This report proposes an ordering system for precast concrete elements (PCEs) at the building, component, and connector scales. Diagrams and text illustrate and describe these scales and their relations and, at the same time, present a visualization and naming convention of physical attributes of PCEs.

The report presents knowledge of PCEs at three scales: building, component, and connector. The primary findings are captured in five diagrams (Figure 1, Figure 7, Figure 9, Figure 16, and Figure 17) where the three scales are ordered separately and then combined into a common naming convention. The report's structure follows the three scales. After an introduction describing the methodology, sections studying the building, component, and connector scales follow. The concluding remarks argue that future increased reuse of PCEs not only depends on studying individual PCEs but also on the knowledge of properties at different scales.

Understanding the material and functional aspects that influence PCEs is an often-overlooked step in making elements available for reuse. In this report, both quantitative and qualitative aspects are analysed at three scales in order to capture and connect their impact on PCEs. First of all, when PCEs are combined at the building scale, their properties constrain and are constrained by the structures and functions proposed. Structural and functional typologies of buildings are, therefore, more or less suited to certain element typologies (as shown in Figure 6). At the component scale, PCE properties and characteristics are analysed and compared from historical and BIM perspectives (as shown in Figure 9). When elements are joined, their properties at the connector scale determine and are determined by the type of connector used. As a result, certain elements are better suited for or more commonly used with certain connectors (as shown in Figures Figure 16 and Figure 17). The closeness of the relationships between PCEs, their connectors and the structural systems they form is thus uncovered.

Further, this report proposes a common nomenclature (as shown in Figure 1) for PCEs at the three scales. The nomenclature covers the main categories for classifying PCEs for reuse. The typological names that accompany the additional diagrams and charts in the report serve as a reference for a deeper reading and classifying of PCEs at the three scales. The report is a step on the path towards describing a comprehensive taxonomy of precast building systems. The taxonomy will be a framework and guideline for classifying precast systems, elements and structural details. It will act as a general knowledge base for PCE reuse and support to the process of creating a digital element database.

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	5
1.1. Methodology of the report.....	6
2. Building scale.....	7
2.1. Structural typologies.....	8
2.2. Functional typologies.....	10
3. Component scale.....	13
3.1. Element subcategories.....	16
3.2. Distribution of elements in a system.....	20
4. Connector scale.....	22
4.1. Force transfer mechanisms.....	24
5. Conclusion.....	30
References.....	31

1. Introduction

The ReCreate project researches deconstruction and reuse of precast concrete elements that have not been originally designed for disassembly (Huuhka *et al.*, 2023). In the course of this project, a large variety of precast concrete buildings and systems are identified and studied. The purpose of the current report is to develop a nomenclature and a preliminary conceptual framework for a comprehensive understanding of precast systems, summarised in Figure 1 and elaborated on in Chapters 2, 3, and 4. The framework acts as a basis for ordering and classifying precast systems according to their essential typological properties. The aim is to enable identifying relations, i.e. common and shared features, and separating features, of systems.

This is an initial step towards a comprehensive ‘taxonomy’ of precast building systems, which will be reported in full in a future ReCreate deliverable D1.3. The taxonomy, then again, is a key tool in evaluating technology transfer possibilities pertaining to deconstruction and reuse from one context to another, in particular from the ReCreate piloting countries (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands and Germany) to other EU countries, and beyond. The reader should also keep in mind that to determine whether the elements of a given donor building are suitable for reuse, a proper pre-demolition audit (Vullings *et al.*, 2022) and a quality management procedure (Räsänen *et al.*, 2024) must be followed.

D1.2 Hernández Vargas, J. & Stenberg, E. (2024) Diagram 1 - Main typologies at the building, component and connection scale

Figure 1. Diagram showing the three scales of typologies. Structural typologies are shown at the building scale, main PCE typologies at the component scale, and predominant joints (force-transfer mechanisms) at the connector scale. Recreate country-cluster pilots are shown colour-coded at the different scales.

1.1. Methodology of the report

Through the analysis of the four country cluster donor buildings in ReCreate Work Package 1 (WPI), large amounts of source material have been collected. This material has been used to produce country-specific dossiers on precast concrete building systems (mainly digital folders of files and some physical material) for both ReCreate partner countries (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany) and ReCreate target countries in East Europe with large prefabricated building stocks (e.g. Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Czechia, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria). The dossiers have been collected and edited in workshops with the generous help of ReCreate partners. The form of the dossiers is based on the methods of collecting and analysing source material of precast structural systems that have been discussed and shared by ReCreate partners in workshops. The dossiers have been further informed by previous work done at KTH such as Structural Systems of the Million Program Era (Stenberg, 2013), studies of the global spread of prefabricated concrete components done in collaboration with Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile such as Flying Panels (Alonso & Palmarola, 2019), and earlier mappings of structural systems such as Monolith Controversies (Alonso & Palmarola, 2014).

The developed framework builds primarily on two previous works. First, the architectural handbook *'Constructing Architecture'* (Deplazes, 2005), which 'aims to show how much architectural expression depends on its constructional composition' through the theory of tectonics and a systematic analysis and interdependence of three scales of construction: materials, elements and structures. Building on this understanding, this ReCreate report aims to introduce through diagrams the relationships and interdependencies that individual PCE types (the element scale in Deplazes [2005]) have with the type of building or structure the PCEs are present in (the structures scale in Deplazes [2005]) and the connector types used to join the PCEs (the material scale in Deplazes [2005]). By introducing architectural tectonics into the reuse discourse, an analogous understanding of how materials, building parts, and whole structures are related across their different scales is proposed.

Second, the engineering handbook *'Planning and design handbook on precast building structures'* (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014), which argues that building with precast structures is a building technology in itself, not a lesser version of in-situ cast structures, that has fundamental advantages for the contemporary construction sector. It also recognizes that 'structural form follows function' and covers the relationships between PCEs, their joints, and the structural systems they form. The handbook, for example, lists 'a limited number of basic structural systems of which the design principles are more or less identical: portal and skeletal structures, wall frame structures, floor and roof structures and facades in architectural concrete' in which PCEs occur.

The engineering and architectural knowledge of construction in general and PCEs in particular contained within these handbooks does not cover the aspect of a building's lifecycle that involves reuse. Therefore, the aim of this report is to link the use of terminology

from both the architecture and engineering disciplines and develop it into a reuse nomenclature.

Similar to the above-described extension of new construction knowledge into reuse knowledge, a historical and technological analysis of existing precast concrete buildings has been an important part of developing a reuse understanding. For example, Lewicki's (1966) *'Building with Large Prefabricates'* is one of the earliest and most comprehensive sources of knowledge on building prefabricates. Much of this analysis involves examining and reading historical source material, such as technical and architectural drawings and manuals, from precast systems. For instance, overall quantification of element types can often be found in building scheduling and factory planning documents. Other historical sources such as industrial brochures, journal articles, and technical reports also provide important input for key terms and definitions, besides often describing the planning and execution of PCEs in a more comprehensive way.

2. Building scale

A precast structural system can be defined as a set of technical construction elements that have been developed to make sure that 'all components correspond, that assembly can proceed without complications' (Schmid and Testa, 1969). A precast system ensures the consistent assembly of individual PCEs, adhering to a predefined set of guidelines that ensure modularity and standardisation. The system comprises both the set of structural members and their possible configurations. Furthermore, precast systems standardise element production, labour, work routines, machinery, and processes.

While in many cases precast systems encompass complete structures, precast systems may also be understood in various degrees of prefabrication, where precast construction is complemented with in-situ concrete or other building materials. Precast systems that constitute the entirety of the building are referred to as total-precast-concrete systems (Wilden, 2010), where all the elements are supplied by a single or various manufacturers following a common standard. Alternatively, complementary precast systems (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014) provide specific solutions for specific parts of a building, such as floors, roofs, and facades.

Configurations of precast concrete systems can be generally divided into structural typologies (Section 2.1) and functional typologies (Section 2.2). Structural typologies are based on the technical and load-bearing properties of PCEs. For example, structures requiring larger spans use a portal-frame typology, while smaller room-size spans are solved using wall-frame typologies. Functional typologies, on the other hand, are based on the spatial requirements of the intended use of the structure. For example, non-residential retail buildings require large open spaces for the display of goods, whereas residential multi-family buildings require many small rooms.

In the case of housing, where standardised units are repeated to constitute a building, a modular approach is often applied. This allows buildings to be described as a discrete number of independent staircases that can be further subdivided into individual flats or residential units. Within each unit, a specific configuration of precast elements is established, allowing for a precise estimation of the required components for each construction, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Common nomenclature for precast residential buildings, which are most commonly made out of repetitions of a vertical circulation module, which in turn can be subdivided into individual flats or housing units.

2. 1. Structural typologies

The most predominant structural typologies used in precast concrete construction include portal-frame, skeletal, wall-frame, and cell structures (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014), which are illustrated in Figure 3.

Portal-frame structures

Portal-frame structures primarily consist of column and beam elements with rigid connections. These structures are characterised by their large spans and are therefore particularly suited for industrial buildings. A typical portal frame typically allows spans between 15 and 40 meters. This configuration enables large open spaces most commonly as single-story buildings with large open areas, typically used for industrial warehouses.

Figure 3. Main structural typologies for precast concrete systems. Structural typologies are also highly correlated to functional typologies. For instance, portal-frame structures are particularly suited to industrial buildings that require extensive unobstructed spaces. In contrast, for residential buildings wall-frame structures constitute the most cost-effective alternative, as load-bearing walls double down as delimitating living spaces.

Skeletal structures

Skeletal structures are defined by a network of columns and beams constituting a three-dimensional frame that supports the building. This configuration allows for greater flexibility in the layout of the building and facade design, without imposing a particular interior partition, making it well-suited for office, commercial, and some residential buildings.

Wall-frame structures

Wall-frame structures are defined by load-bearing walls providing spatial partitions in the plan. In some cases, these structures may include column elements to free interior space. Wall-frame structures can be further classified according to the main orientation of the load-bearing walls, as follows.

Integral wall

In this configuration, load-bearing walls run longitudinally and transversely relative to the building block, with room-sized spans. Main divisions in the plan typically correspond to load-bearing walls, while other minor non-structural precast elements may be added as functional partition non-load-bearing walls. These internal wall elements often include

door openings, that accommodate internal circulations. In this configuration, slabs are often solid concrete elements spanning in two directions.

Cross wall

Cross-wall structures, also known as bookshelf structures, feature load-bearing transverse walls from which slabs span in the longitudinal direction, either using solid or hollow-core slabs. Spans can range from room-sized to flat-sized, with the latter involving spans larger made possible by using hollow core slabs. The larger flat-sized internal spans are favourable for the flexible arrangement (and rearrangement) of internal spaces. Additional internal load-bearing walls may be added to brace the structure.

Spine wall

In spine wall structures, also known as load-bearing exterior wall structures, the slabs are oriented in the transverse direction of the building. When the breadth of the building surpasses the span capacity of the floor elements, an internal spine wall, also called a heart wall, is placed along the longitudinal axis of the building. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014). There can also be two internal spine walls encasing a corridor, bathrooms, and/or stairs at the core of the building. This typology allows for flexible plan arrangements that can be partitioned by non-load-bearing walls.

Cell systems

Precast elements can also be developed as cell, modular, or volumetric components, that are produced off-site and assembled as stacked room-sized elements. This type of precast structure is particularly suitable for applications with large amounts of installations and technical requirements, where industrialised production in a controlled environment replaces on-site labour. Although there are complete structures built with cell components, entire structures like housing units, hotels, and prisons; cell systems are predominately used for specific sections of a building, such as bathrooms or technical units. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

2. 2. Functional typologies

The specific technical characteristics of the different structural systems mentioned in the previous section are intrinsically linked to the specific functional requirements for the type of building in question: residential, commercial, industrial, offices, etc. These building typologies can be arranged under different criteria. In their paper on the study of the material stock of the built environment, Lanau *et al.*, (2019) provide a hierarchical classification, with buildings and infrastructure as the two main branches (Figure 4).

From this tree representation, certain categories are highlighted as more relevant sources of precast elements for reuse (Figure 5). Conversely, the design handbook for precast structures (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014) pairs building typologies that correspond to similar structural principles, although they may be classified under separate branches as they belong to different societal sectors. For instance, offices and administrative buildings or

hotels and hospitals have similar structural requirements. These main building typologies for reuse are contrasted to the structural types that are most often found in the documented cases, described as a relational matrix indicating the correspondence between building types and structural systems, as illustrated in Figure 6.

The high demand for housing after the Second World War was the driving force for the development of many precast systems in Europe (Bachmann and Steinle, 2012a). However, the use of industrialised precast quickly expanded to many non-residential such as educational, industrial and office buildings.

Figure 4. Classification of the built environment. Adapted from Lanau et al. (2019) with permission.

Figure 5. A hierarchical representation of the built environment highlighting the typologies most relevant for ReCreate. Based on the categories described by Lanau et al. (2019).

Diagram 2 - System scale typologies

D1.2 Hernández Vargas, J. & Stenberg, E. (2024)

Figure 6. Correspondence between building typologies and structural systems.

3. Component scale

This chapter compares the geometric component typologies with the technical classes driven by current digital building practices.

Geometric classification

First, at the component scale, the classification of PCEs starts by determining overall categories that correspond to common building components such as beams, columns, slabs, and walls. Drawing from the conceptual framework proposed by Lewicki (1966), precast elements are ordered based on their geometry and proportions, separating them into block, panel, and linear elements. Room-size components with two long dimensions (slabs and walls) are referred to as panels, extruded components with one long dimension (posts and beams) are called linear elements, while thicker and shorter components are referred to as blocks. This geometric classification underlines the spatial dimension of the components, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 7. Classification of precast concrete elements according to their proportions. Redrawn from (Lewicki, 1966).

Beyond Lewicki’s geometric distinction, the classification of PCEs at the component scale can be based on the forces each element is designed to withstand. This typology is structural and intrinsically linked to the dimensions, amount, and location of reinforcement in the components. Technical literature and design handbooks for PCEs prefer to group

concrete components into partial systems (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014), such as beam-columns, floor, and facade systems of components.

From the perspective of the production of PCEs, similar categories of components can be found. For example, in the Swedish context, a catalogue of factories manufacturing PCEs lists the following relevant component categories: Wall elements, Slabs and Roofs, Stairs, Balconies, Columns, Beams, and Frames (Cementa, 1965).

Returning to the proposition that the component scale in ReCreate corresponds to the element scale in Constructing Architecture (Deplazes 2005), a comparison can also be made between the types of PCE components under study and the element types described therein. The element types in Construction Architecture are Foundation/Plinth, Wall, Opening, Floor, Roof, and Stairs/Lifts. Both of these sources of elements correspond well to both Lewicki and the IFC standards in terms of component typologies.

By comparing the component categories with other sources from the construction sector having different perspectives, it seems that the ordering of PCEs into block, panel (wall and slab) and linear (post and beam) components is generally acceptable. In addition, stair and roof slab elements are included because of their reuse potential.

IFC element types

In today's construction industry, heavily reliant on Building Information Modelling (BIM), the classification of components is based on the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) standard. The IFC standard organises building parts in a hierarchical structure. Components are organised according to their properties and relationships to other components.

The IFCs provide a consistent framework to describe elements in a construction project (ISO, 2020). The IFC classification framework organises precast components in a detailed hierarchy that encapsulates their physical characteristics, material properties, and interconnections with additional architectural elements. This stratification fosters a nuanced and interconnected digital representation, fundamental for BIM processes. The IFC protocols facilitate the comprehensive modelling of precast units, encompassing their production, installation, and considerations pertinent to environmental sustainability and lifecycle evaluation.

At the scale of individual PCEs, the foremost classification derives from grouping them by their structural role in the building, i.e., as walls, columns, slabs, roofs, beams, foundations, and stairs (Figure 8). These elements are grouped under the category 'IfcBuiltElement' (5.4.3.4) and can be conceptualised and modelled as variations of the same parametric object, akin to a family of building components. This process is key for building a comprehensive database of precast elements contained in each building (Matthews *et al.*, 2024). The correspondences between Lewicki's geometric classification and the current IFC classification used in BIM are summarised in Figure 9.

Balconies are often defined as a separate category, as in Cementa, (1965), even if from a structural perspective, these elements correspond to shorter wall and slab elements that form the balconies. While the geometrical classification from Lewicki and the IFC framework would list these elements as walls or slabs, they are different as they are exposed elements.

Figure 8. Classes defined in the IFC standard (5.4.3.4 IfcBuildingElement, n.d.). Relevant classes for PCEs are highlighted.

IFC		Lewicki						
		IfcBeam	IfcColumn	IfcFooting	IfcRoof	IfcSlab	IfcStair	IfcWall
Block								●
				●				
Panel								●
					●	●		
Post / Beam			●					
		●						
N/A							●	

D1.2 Hernández Vargas, J. & Stenberg, E. (2024) Diagram 3 - Component scale

Figure 9. Correspondence between the proportional definitions by Lewicki (1966) and the building element types defined by the IFC Standard (ISO, 2020).

3. 1. Element subcategories

Based on the previously mentioned classification for building elements, a general classification can be discerned based on structural roles and architectural requirements. This is done by listing the main subcategories for each type of PCE derived from the previous classification. For example, even if floor and roof elements perform different architectural and structural roles, Lewicki’s (1966) classification as horizontally spanning elements is comparable to the shared category of floor/roof precast systems, where roof elements can be understood as a lightweight subset of the same element type featuring longer spans and reduced weight (cf. Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Columns

Precast concrete columns are structural elements that provide vertical support to the structural frame of a building, transferring loads from beams (Section 3.1.2) and slabs (Section 3.1.4) down to the foundations. Engineered for strength and stability, columns come in various shapes and sizes, such as rectangular, circular, or custom profiles, to meet specific architectural demands. The minimal cross-sectional dimension for precast concrete columns is generally set at 300 mm to facilitate handling and provide sufficient space for beam-column connections and tolerances. A 400-mm dimension ensures a two-hour fire resistance (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014). Large precast structures may feature columns up to 24 metres high, although single-storey elements are predominant.

Beams

Beams (Figure 10) are horizontal structural components that bear the loads from slab or roof elements (Section 3.1.4) and transmit these forces to columns or walls. Precast concrete beams are efficient: they facilitate long spans and flexible building layouts. In addition to the usual rectangular profile (a), they can be designed in various cross-sectional shapes. L-shaped beams (b) and inverted T-beams (c) can help to optimise structural performance and accommodate architectural needs. They are especially important in portal-frame and skeletal structures. I-beams (d) are mostly found in industrial buildings with large spans either with constant height or as rafters (e) of variable height. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 10. Subcategories for precast beams.

Walls

Precast concrete walls (Figure 11) can serve both structural and non-structural purposes, ranging from load-bearing walls that contribute to the building's stability to cladding panels that provide architectural facade systems. Precast walls can be manufactured with insulation, installations, window or door openings, and surface textures. Precast wall elements can be classified into interior and exterior elements.

While the dimensions for doorways and windows can be flexible, many manufacturers lean towards standard sizes for efficiency. Stability considerations during demoulding and handling necessitate minimum dimensions for lintels and mullions, both between windows and at the edges of panels.

Figure 11. Subcategories for precast wall elements.

Facade elements

Facade systems represent the external skin of a building, playing a crucial role in defining its architectural character and environmental performance. Precast concrete facade panels can integrate insulation and customized design and details, including finished doors and windows (a). These panels can be non-load bearing, or designed as structural elements that contribute to the building's overall stability. Facade elements are commonly manufactured as so-called 'sandwich' panels, comprising two layers of concrete separated by a layer of insulation. The outer layer, exposed to the environment, is typically designed for aesthetic appeal and durability, while the inner layer contributes to the structural integrity of the building. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Interior walls

Wall elements in precast concrete serve various functions, from defining spaces within a building to providing acoustic and fire separation between different areas (b). Depending on the building's design, interior precast walls can be load-bearing, playing a part in the structural integrity of the construction, or non-structural. precast walls with large openings (c) are commonly classified separately as frame elements (Lewicki, 1966), which contribute to the structural framework as shear walls.

Parapets

Parapets are short wall elements commonly used at the edges of roofs and balconies, serving as safety barriers, and completing the facade (d). Precast parapets offer uniformity and can be integrated with facade systems for a cohesive architectural expression. They can also serve structural functions, such as wind bracing or anchoring for roof elements.

Slab and roof elements

Precast floor and roof systems (Figure 12) are often defined as sub-systems, which can be classified into fully precast floors and semi-precast floors. Fully precast elements are completely done at the factory whereas semi-precast floor systems use a combination of precast elements that are complemented with on-site cast concrete. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Precast concrete floors can be subdivided into massive slabs (a), hollow-core slabs (b), ribbed floors (c), composite floors (d), and beam-and-block floor systems (e). They are usually constructed in 300 mm modules, with 600, 1200, and 2400 mm being the most common measurements. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 12. Subcategories for precast slab and roof elements.

Massive slab elements

Massive slab elements (a) are solid reinforced concrete elements. These slabs are ideal for applications where structural integrity and fire resistance are paramount. Due to their mass, they also provide excellent acoustic insulation and thermal mass and therefore are mostly found in residential buildings.

Hollow-core slabs

Hollow-core slab elements (b) are characterized by void cores that span longitudinally to reduce the weight of the element. Most commonly hollow-core slabs are manufactured using prestressed long-line extrusions or slip-form processes, in beds that are typically 1200 mm wide and up to 180 metres long. Alternatively, shorter reinforced hollow-core elements are cast in moulds. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Ribbed floor elements

Ribbed floor elements (c) are suitable for medium to long spans, offering architectural flexibility and the ability to integrate mechanical and electrical services within the ribbed profile. Ribbed slabs are available in various configurations including double-tee, single-tee, and U-shaped elements.

Composite floor plates

Composite floor plates (d) combine precast concrete with in-situ concrete topping, creating a unified structural element that leverages the benefits of both construction methods. The precast component acts as permanent formwork and can provide immediate working platforms, while the in-situ concrete ensures a monolithic action, enhancing the load-bearing capacity and stiffness of the floor system.

Beam-and-block floor systems

Beam-and-block floor systems (e) consist of a series of inverted T-beams with infill blocks placed between them. This system is quick to install, requiring no formwork on site, and provides a flat soffit ready for direct application of finishes. Beam-and-block systems are commonly used in residential construction, offering a practical solution for ground floors and basements.

Roof elements

Specialised roof elements (f) are mostly used in industrial and commercial buildings, and in sports facilities, and are characterised by their capacity to cover large spans by using slender cross-sections that reduce self-weight.

Stairs

Precast elements allow for a high degree of finishing that can be fabricated precisely under controlled conditions. Stair components (Figure 13) can be manufactured in straight stair elements (a), either with integrated or separated landings. Monolithic stair modules include spiral stairs (b) and monoblock stair units (c) (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 13. Subcategories for precast stairs.

Foundation elements

Foundation elements, such as piles, footings, and grade beams, form the crucial interface between a structure and the ground. Pocket foundation elements are commonly used in suitable soil conditions, where precast foundations offer a time-effective alternative compared with their in-situ cast counterparts. Similarly, precast foundation walls offer rapid construction times, which is especially critical in cold climates where demoulding times are extended. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

3. 2. Distribution of elements in a system

Individual building components are specified as types, from which several instances are most often found within the same structure. Each building element can be modelled as an individual element, which can be then assembled to form a complete model for the building. For example, Figure 14 illustrates the process of compiling geometrical information from individual elements and its integration into a digital model of a whole building section.

Figure 14. System Skarne 66 (Sweden) and their main structural components form the original technical drawings (left) and as a digital 3D model (right).

To further understand the arrangement of elements that constitute a system, the overall dimensions of each element can be plotted to reveal the dispersion of distinct types within the system. In Figure 15, all the elements are aligned in Cartesian space to define the largest dimension on each axis. This method allows the creation of a ‘fingerprint’ of each building, that shows a concise overview of the dispersion of element types and the individual quantities involved. Alignments resulting from common features such as floor heights and standard modules, can also be observed.

Figure 15. Comparison of the ‘fingerprint’ tool showing the types of elements used in System Skarne 66 (Sweden) and BES (Finland). Dot size indicates the number of elements of each type whereas colour corresponds to the main component categories.

4. Connector scale

Connectors play a key role in prefabricated structures. They ensure the consistent and reliable transfer of forces among individual elements, integrating them into a unified structural entity. While doing so, they must simultaneously accommodate other stresses from thermal displacement, shrinkage, creep, fire, etc (Engström *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, connectors are critical for ensuring structural safety. More importantly, the design of connectors dictates how easily the elements can be separated and removed without damaging the components, which is essential for enabling reuse (Huuhka *et al.*, 2023).

This includes foundation walls to the foundational structure, ensuring the desired collective behaviour of precast subsystems, such as floor diaphragm action and wall shear action, and directing forces to the stabilising structure. Additionally, connections play a role in fulfilling specific aesthetic and functional requirements, such as durability and visual appeal, and their detailing must accommodate the manufacturing, transportation, and assembly of precast components (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

The diverse array of connectors can be classified using different criteria, reflecting the variety in purpose, properties, and applications. In precast structures, connections can be separated into two main types: permanent connections that are part of the service life of the structure, and construction connectors that facilitate lifting or temporarily securing the element in place until other elements of the structure support it. This report will focus only on permanent connections, which can be classified further into wet and dry connections. Wet connections involve the use of concrete or grout to achieve the bond between the elements. Conversely, dry connections use mechanical methods for joining elements.

Figure 16 shows the correspondence between different pairs of elements being connected, with the most commonly found connections marked in green and less-common connections in yellow. Empty connection pairs may still be found in particular cases but correspond to elements that are normally not linked structurally, as in the case of columns and walls that belong to two different structural systems, skeletal and wall-frame systems respectively. Similarly, Figure 17 elaborates on the different types of elements and connections typically used to connect them, which are discussed next.

Diagram 4 - Connector matrix

D1.2 Hernández Vargas, J. & Stenberg, E. (2024)

Figure 16. Diagram showing the most common component-to-component connections. Connection pairs between the same element are listed next to the element's name, whereas cells represent possible connections between pairs of elements.

		Elements						
		Wall	Slab	Roof	Column	Beam	Stair	Foundation
Force-locking	Bolting	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Dowels	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Friction	●	●					
	Post-tensioning		●			●		
Cohesive	Bond	●	●		●	●		
	Anchoring of bars	●	●		●	●		
	Welding		●	●	●			
Form-fitting	Encasing				●	●		●
	Interlock	●	●		●	●	●	
	Staggered joints	●						

● Common ● Less common

Diagram 5 - Connector typologies

D1.2 Hernández Vargas, J. & Stenberg, E. (2024)

Figure 17. Classification of connector types and elements involved.

4. 1. Force transfer mechanisms

In the technical literature, the classification of mechanical connections are classified under different criteria that often lead to overlapping categories or hybrid principles. Specialised literature classifies structural connections by the main type of force involved, compression, tension, shear, torsion, or bending forces (Engström *et al.*, 2008; Bachmann and Steinle, 2012b), while others refer specifically to the type of hardware in use (Wilden, 2010) While these descriptions are useful for structural design, they are too abstract or too specific and offer limited insights on the applicability of these principles in connecting precast elements. Connection types in this section correspond to the force-transfer mechanisms described in the fib bulletin 74 (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014), further classified into three categories defined by the main mechanical principle used: force-locking, cohesive, and form-fitting

connections. Force-locking connections depend on the application of force to maintain the connection between elements, such as friction, tensile or compressive forces. Cohesive connections involve a material bond between the parts, creating material continuity using adhesives, welding, grouting, or other material fusing or merging the parts. Form-fitting connections rely on interlocking geometry to prevent movement between the parts, without relying on friction or adhesion. These three categories are most often mentioned in the German literature (Stupré, 1987). It is important to remark that these force-transfer mechanisms are most often combined in different ways to achieve the requirements for the connection. For example, connections between walls and floor elements often combine friction and dowel action (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Force-locking connections

In force-locking connections (Figure 18), the parts are held together primarily by frictional forces between their contacting surfaces. This is usually achieved by applying an external force, such as in bolted or clamped connections, where the tight fit generates friction that holds the parts together (Stupré, 1987). These connections can resist forces in certain directions depending on the nature and magnitude of the applied force.

Figure 18. Transfer mechanisms based on force locking.

Bolting

Bolting is a prevalent method for connecting precast elements, primarily utilised to transfer tensile and shear forces efficiently. The bolting mechanism involves the use of various anchoring systems, including bolts, threaded sockets, rails, or captive nuts, which are embedded within the precast units. For example, Figure 18 shows a bolted connection between a column and a foundation. These anchoring elements provide the necessary mechanical interlock required to resist applied loads. The connection details are designed with oversized holes in the connecting members to accommodate construction tolerances, allowing for some adjustability during assembly. Bolting offers the advantage of rapid assembly and disassembly, making it suitable for temporary structures or situations where future modifications might be required or where acoustic and fire-resistance demands are low. The strength and reliability of bolted connections depend significantly on the quality of the anchoring system, the bolt material, and the precision of the installation process. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Dowels

Dowel action refers to the mechanism where steel bars, partially embedded in concrete, transfer shear forces across a joint in precast structures (Engström *et al.*, 2008). This mechanism is akin to a beam on an elastic foundation, where the bar acts as a dowel pin experiencing varying concrete stresses and bearing stresses, particularly near the joint face, as depicted in Figure 18. The dowel pin is subject to shear forces and bending moments, potentially leading to different failure modes depending on the strength and placement of the bar relative to the concrete element. A weak bar may fail in shear, while a strong bar in a weak element or with inadequate concrete cover may cause element splitting. Proper design and detailing of the connection zone are vital to spreading the concentrated reaction safely, utilising reinforcement to control splitting effects and employing the strut-and-tie method for equilibrium in cracked concrete scenarios. This ensures the effective transfer of shear forces and the integrity of the connection in precast concrete assemblies (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Friction

Friction-based connections rely on the roughness of joint interfaces to transfer shear forces, depending on compressive stresses at the interface to generate sufficient friction resistance, as schematically presented in Figure 18. This compressive force may stem from gravity loads or be induced by prestressing. When direct compressive forces are unattainable, reinforcing bars placed across the joint can be strained under shear load, leading to joint separation, tension in the bars, and consequently, induced compressive forces across the interface. This phenomenon, known as the shear-friction effect, enhances shear resistance with increased transverse reinforcement and frictional coefficient (Engström *et al.*, 2008). This principle is often applied in grouted longitudinal joints between floor and wall elements, where bond and friction work in tandem to ensure force transfer.

Post-tensioning

Post-tensioning is a specialised technique used predominantly in large-scale structures and erecting tall buildings with precast elements. This method involves laying cable ducts within the precast elements during their fabrication. After the elements are positioned and aligned, prestressing cables are threaded through these ducts. The cables are then tensioned to a predetermined force and subsequently grouted to lock in the tension, effectively compressing the concrete elements together, as represented in Figure 18. This induced compression enhances the elements' ability to resist tensile and shear forces across the joints, contributing to the overall stability and durability of the structure. Post-tensioning not only increases the structural efficiency of precast assemblies but also allows for the construction of slender and more aesthetically pleasing structures by minimizing the need for bulky supports and enabling longer spans between supports. (Engström *et al.*, 2008).

Cohesive connections

Cohesive connections are characterized by the material continuity or cohesion between the connecting elements. This category encompasses connections where adhesives, welding, or the curing of concrete around reinforcement bars create a unified or continuous material phase across the connection, allowing for the transfer of forces. Figure 19 shows the force-transfer mechanisms based on cohesive connections.

Figure 19. Transfer mechanisms based on material interaction.

Cohesive or material connections are made by a material bond between the components, typically at the molecular or atomic level. This can be achieved through processes like welding, soldering, brazing, where a material continuity between the parts is established. The bond can be as strong as the materials themselves and can often provide a permanent connection.

Bond

The bond mechanism involves the adhesion and bonding between different materials, such as between precast concrete elements and cast-in-situ concrete. This type of connection is suitable for managing small interface stresses, often found in composite actions between toppings and precast floors. The efficacy of bond and shear transfer at the interface is influenced by factors such as surface roughness, strength, cleanliness, and the treatment applied to the precast surface. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Anchorage of reinforcement bars

The anchorage of reinforcing bars is a critical aspect in precast concrete structures, especially for steel bars subject to tension. Anchorage can be achieved through several methods, including bond, mechanical devices like hooks, bends, or rods, or by leveraging the pull-out capacity of the concrete (i.e. the adhesion between the concrete and the reinforcement). When anchored by a bond; ribbed, indented, or threaded bars are embedded in concrete, relying on the bond between the bar surface and concrete to transfer tensile forces. Adequate concrete cover and anchorage length are essential to ensure the anchorage capacity surpasses the tensile strength of the bar, preventing failure modes such as splitting of the concrete cover or bond failure (Engström *et al.*, 2008).

Mechanical end anchors, such as heads, bends, or hooks, are used when space constraints limit anchorage length, introducing concentrated forces into the concrete that need careful management to avoid brittle failure, as illustrated in Figure 19.

Welding

Welding is used to join steel components within or attached to precast concrete elements. This method can directly connect protruding steel details, such as overlapping reinforcement bars, providing a continuous load path and ensuring structural integrity at the joints. Alternatively, welding can involve the use of intermediate steel pieces, serving as links between concrete units or between steel components and concrete (as shown in Figure 19). The anchor plates, typically fixed to the concrete by welded bars, rely on bond or mechanical end anchors for secure attachment, following the principles of anchorage previously described. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014). Welding offers a permanent solution for force transfer, particularly effective in transmitting tensile and bending stresses, and requires careful execution to maintain the structural properties of the welded components.

Form-fitting connections

This category refers to connections where the force transfer between elements is primarily achieved through the interlocking shapes or geometries of the connecting parts. These connections do not rely on friction or adhesion but on the direct physical contact and interlock of shapes, which inherently prevents movement or separation of the connected parts under load, as illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Transfer mechanisms based on shape interlocking.

Encasing

Encasing is a force-transfer mechanism used in precast construction where one component is inserted into another, and the gap between them is filled with a bonding material, such as grout or fine concrete. The method primarily transfers compression and bending forces. Encasing can also contribute to shear and torsional resistance by ensuring composite action between the connected elements.

A typical application of encasing is in the connection between a precast column and a foundation designed with a pocket to receive the column, as represented in Figure 20. The

encasing material fills the space around the inserted component, securing it in place and transferring loads between the elements. This method ensures a strong connection capable of transferring compressive forces and, depending on the design, can also aid in transferring bending moments and shear forces through the encased section. (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

Shear interlock

Shear interlock involves transferring shear forces through mechanically interlocked, indented joint faces, effectively preventing significant slip along the joint. The compression forces within the mortar prevent the elements from moving apart under shear loads (Figure 20), typically achieved by reinforcing ties at the top and bottom of the joint, or by placing transverse steel loops along the joint length (Engström *et al.*, 2008). This mechanical locking mechanism ensures effective shear force transfer and structural integrity at the joint.

Staggered joints

In staggered joint configurations, particularly in vertical wall joints, shear forces are transferred by compression in the horizontal part of the joint, as shown in Figure 20. The horizontal force component is counteracted by tie reinforcement positioned above the wall panels. This arrangement allows for the efficient transfer of shear forces between components, ensuring that the load is effectively managed through compression and reinforcing ties, contributing to the overall stability of the wall system (Van Acker *et al.*, 2014).

5. Conclusion

Since most knowledge of precast concrete exists for the purpose of producing new structures (Lewicki, 1966; Schmid and Testa, 1969; Van Acker *et al.*, 2014) maintaining existing structures, or understanding historical structures (Stenberg, 2013; Alonso & Palmarola, 2019), the shift towards reuse (Vullings *et al.*, 2022; Huuhka *et al.*, 2023) involves re-evaluating the general knowledge of precast concrete and specific knowledge of PCEs in a comprehensive manner.

In this report, an analysis of the relationship that individual PCE types have to both functional and structural typologies describe first some general characteristics of PCEs (Figure 6). Further and in order to establish a broad base, a description system of PCE types based on early precast knowledge and current digital practices is introduced (Figure 9). In a similar manner, an analysis of how common connector types are with PCE types is made (Figure 16 and Figure 17). Finally, and with the intention of laying out a nomenclature for reuse of PCEs, the three scales of building, component, and connector are brought together (Figure 1).

This report is a first step and has laid the foundations for a systematic naming (and, therefore, understanding) of precast concrete for reuse purposes, by examining and ordering knowledge of precast concrete at three scales: building, component, and connector. The formulation of a common nomenclature and the assimilation of different classification systems enables a systematic classification of precast systems and the interdependence between their properties across various scales for reuse purposes.

These insights underlay the forthcoming deliverable D1.3 which will provide a deeper analysis through a more detailed and comprehensive taxonomy of precast systems.

References

5.4.3.4 *IfcBuildingElement* (no date). Available at: https://standards.buildingsmart.org/IFC/RELEASE/IFC4_1/FINAL/HTML/schema/ifcproductextension/lexical/ifcbuildingelement.htm (Accessed: 22 February 2024).

Alonso, P.I., Palmarola, H., and ArkDes (eds) (2019) *Flying panels: Flying panels how concrete panels changed the world: published to accompany the exhibition 'Flying panels: how concrete panels changed the world', ArkDes - The Swedish Centre for Architecture and Design, 18 October 2019 - 1 March 2020*. Berlin: DOM publishers.

Bachmann, H. and Steinle, A. (2012a) 'General', in *Precast Concrete Structures*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp. 5–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783433600962.ch1>.

Bachmann, H. and Steinle, A. (2012b) 'Joints between precast concrete elements', in *Precast Concrete Structures*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp. 175–211. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783433600962.ch3>.

Cementa (1965) *Betongvaruindustrin - Katalog över betongvaru- och elementfabriker i Sverige med produktionsinriktning angiven*.

Deplazes, A. (ed.) (2005) *Constructing architecture: materials, processes, structures, a handbook*. Basel ; Boston: Birkhäuser-Publishers for Architecture.

Engström, B., Alexander, S., Cholewicki, A., De Chefdebien, A., Della Bella, B., Elliott, K.S., Fernández, D., Menegotto, M., Newby, M., Rise, G., Romanes, H., Skjelle, A., Tsoukantas, S., Vambersky, N.J.A., Van Acker, A. and Vinje, L. (2008) *fib Bulletin 43. Structural connections for precast concrete buildings*. Lausanne: International Federation for Structural Concrete (fib) (Bulletin / International Federation for Structural Concrete Guide to good practice, 43).

Huuhka, S., Aarika-Stenroos, L., Lahdensivu, J., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Arnold, V., Stenberg, E., Blok, R., Gudmundsson, K., Teuffel, P. and Mettke, A. (2023) 'Recreating the Construction Sector for Circularity: Catalysing the reuse of prefabricated concrete elements', in *The Routledge Handbook of Catalysts for a Sustainable Circular Economy*. Routledge.

ISO (2020) 'SS-EN ISO 16739-1:2020 Standard - Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries'. Available at: <https://www.sis.se/produkter/produktionsteknik/industriell-processtyrning/matning-och-styrning-av-industriella-processer/ss-en-iso-16739-12020/> (Accessed: 19 February 2024).

Lanau, M., Liu, G., Kral, U., Wiedenhofer, D., Keijzer, E., Yu, C. and Ehlert, C. (2019) 'Taking Stock of Built Environment Stock Studies: Progress and Prospects', *Environmental Science & Technology*, 53(15), pp. 8499–8515. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b06652>.

Lewicki, B. (1966) *Building with Large Prefabricates*. Elsevier Publishing Company.

Matthews, B., Mudge, F., Wijte, S., Vullings, M., Lambrechts, T. and Scalbi, A. (2024) *A Database for Reclaimed Precast Concrete Elements*.

Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Lambrechts, T., Vullings, M., Arnold, V., Mettke, A., Fischer, J. and Huuhka, S. (2024) *Properties and quality of precast concrete elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots*.

Schmid, T. and Testa, C. (1969) *Systems building. An international survey of methods, (engl., dt., franz.)*. London: Pall Mall.

Stenberg, E. (2013) *Structural Systems of the Million Program Era*. KTH School of Architecture. Available at: <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kth:diva-164319> (Accessed: 13 December 2022).

Stupré (1987) *Kraftschlüssige Verbindungen im Fertigteilbau. 1: Konstruktionsatlas. 2., überarb. Aufl.* Düsseldorf: Beton-Verlag.

Van Acker, A., Chastre, Carlos, Crisp, B., Fernández, D.G., Da Guia Lúcio, V.J., Elliott, K.S., Hughes, S., Jones, G.H., Klein-Holte, R., Maas, S., Menegotto, M., Tsoukantas, S. and Van Der Zee, P. (eds) (2014) *fib Bulletin 74. Planning and design handbook on precast building structures*. Lausanne, Switzerland: International Federation for Structural Concrete (fib) (Bulletin Manual-textbook, 74 / International Federation for Structural Concrete).

Vullings, M., Wijte, S. and Huuhka, S. (2022) *Guidelines for a BIM-aided pre-deconstruction audit. The ReCreate project*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5f54ee881&appId=PPGMS>.

Wilden, H. (ed.) (2010) *PCI design handbook: precast and prestressed concrete*. 7th ed. Chicago: Precast/Prestressed Concrete Institute.